

ISic0283

I.Sicily inscription 0283

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tauromenium

Place of origin (modern)

Taormina

Provenance

Theatre, 1841

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Taormina, Antiquarium del
Teatro Antico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---][A]ϋg IIvir
2. [---][po]nt[i]fex
3. [---]

Apparatus

Text of Manganaro 1989

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175757

EDR 081500

EDCS 21900314

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.6995 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650752>)

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1989.0339d

Manganaro, G. 1989. Iscrizioni Latine nuove e vecchie della Sicilia. *Epigraphica*. 51: 161-196. At 166 no.26 fig.26

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